

Sonochemical quaternization of poly(4-vinyl pyridine) with iodoethane and study of its sorption of Cr^{VI}

P. Chowdhury*, K. Roy, P. Mondal and S. P. Bayen

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235, West Bengal, India

E-mail : pranesh_02@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : Quantitative quaternization of poly(4-vinyl pyridine) (P4VP) with iodoethane was carried out in green aqueous medium with the help of ultrasound. The resulting resin was used to remove and recover Cr^{VI} from the aqueous solution. Batch adsorption studies have been carried out to determine the effect of metal ion concentration, sorbent dose, pH, temperature and the presence of competitive ions. The process was found to be pH and solid/liquid ratio dependent. The sorption capacities increased with the increase of Cr^{VI} concentration and the resin exhibits good efficiency in the removal of chromium at wide range of pH. Equilibrium modeling of the process of metal ion sorption was carried out by using Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. The experimental data obey these isotherm models. Competitive sorption studies revealed the selectivity property of the quaternized product towards chromium ions. The selectivity is explained by the interaction of transition metal anion with the positively charged two pyridine ring and the formation of sandwich arrangement.

Keywords : Quaternization, poly(4-vinyl pyridine), sorption, Cr^{VI}.

Introduction

Cationic polyelectrolytes, in general, have many potential applications in sludge dewatering¹, design of new membrane², phase transfer catalysis³, ion exchange separation⁴ and stabilization of dispersions⁵ (as lubricating agents, emulsifier, flocculating agents, etc.). Most outstanding examples of cationic polyelectrolyte are quaternary ammonium polymers. Diallyl dimethyl ammonium chloride⁶ (DDAC), methacryloyloxy ethyl trimethyl ammonium chloride⁷ (METAC) and vinyl benzyl trimethyl ammonium chloride⁸ (VBTAC) are some commercially available quaternary ammonium monomers which lead to quaternary ammonium polymers. Preparation of vinyl pyridinium monomers is difficult due to their spontaneous polymerization yielding pyridinium moieties in the main chain⁹. Many studies have been carried out involving the quaternization of poly(4-vinyl pyridine)^{10,11} and related compounds with alkyl and aryl halides. A recently available macro porous resin, ReillexTM HPQ¹², which is derived from poly(4-vinyl pyridine) by quaternization to the extent of about 70% and is reported to offer much

higher resistance to oxidation than conventional strong base polystyrene anion exchanger resins¹², Amberlite IRA-400. Typically, 65–70% quaternization is most common with alkyl halides. Quantitative quaternization¹⁰ of poly(4-vinyl pyridine) and the preparation of quaternized poly(4-vinyl pyridine) nanoparticles¹³ are important goal to be achieved. Moreover, most of the quaternization reactions are carried out in polar organic solvents^{10–14} such as tetrahydrofuran, dimethyl formamide, methanol, etc. Quaternized and cross-linked copolymers from vinyl pyridine and di-halo organic compound are formed spontaneously at ambient temperature by just mixing the two monomers in bulk, in solution or on suspension. The main disadvantage here is the uncontrolled molecular weight of the resulted polymers.

It is noteworthy to mention here that in spite of very high sorption selectivity of Cr^{VI} anions on commercial organic anion-exchange resin¹², Amberlite IRA-400, recovery of chromate from cooling tower blow down is not yet commercially popular. The slow oxidation of the resins by Cr^{VI} and consequent loss of resin capacity pre-

vented more frequent application of the ion exchange process¹⁵. In this context, it may be noted that quaternized poly(vinyl pyridine)^{16,17} has been shown to exhibit greater stability to chemical attack and radiolysis degradation than polystyrene. The greater stability of quaternized poly(vinyl pyridine) to chemical oxidation is exhibited due to the electron deficiency of its ring system.

The remarkable oxidation resistance of the quaternized poly(vinyl pyridine) and its very high selectivity of chromate interested us to search green technique for quantitative quaternization of poly(4-vinyl pyridine) and to develop a suitable method for selective sorption and desorption of Cr^{VI} from aqueous solutions of wide pH range (from acidic to basic) using the quaternized polymer. The measured sorption and desorption properties are compared with those of a commercially available resin ReillexTM HPQ and IRA-400.

Experimental

Materials :

Poly(4-vinyl pyridine) (P4VP) (2% cross-linked) (Sigma Aldrich, USA) was used as the base polymer. Iodoethane (99% pure) (Sigma Aldrich, USA) was used for quaternization of P4VP. Potassium dichromate (Pfizer Ltd., India) was used for the preparation of stock solution (1000 mg L⁻¹). All the working solutions were prepared by proper dilution of stock solution with distilled water. 1,5-Diphenyl carbazide used for the colorimetric estimation¹⁶ of Cr^{VI} was of analytical grade (Merck, India). Methylene blue stain (Merck, India) was used to determine specific surface area¹⁶ of the quaternized poly(4-vinyl pyridine), QP4VP.

Quaternization of poly(4-vinyl pyridine) :

The quaternization was performed with the help of ultrasound using a sonicator (Branson 1510) in aqueous medium in the presence of quaternizing agent. P4VP (colorless, 2.62 g) was soaked with 1.35 g iodoethane in 20 ml distilled water, and subjected to sonication at room temperature for just an hour. The reaction mixture was then centrifuged to obtain a solid (yellow) which was washed several times with water and alcohol, filtered and dried under vacuum at room temperature to a constant weight (3.93 g). The quaternized poly(4-vinyl pyridine), QP4VP was characterized by chemical (iodide analysis),

spectral (FTIR) and thermal (TGA and DTA) analysis. The novelty of the present quaternization method was quantitative as well as green. The degree of quaternization was determined by the reported method³. The shift of the 1600 cm⁻¹ FTIR band of the pyridine ring to 1640 cm⁻¹ is due to quaternization. The reaction was considered quantitative since the band at 1600 cm⁻¹ disappeared almost completely. The extent of quaternization was 98–99%. In the present case green solvent (water) was used in place of widely used organic polar solvents.

Iodide analysis :

The quaternization yield was followed by analysis of the iodide of the final product. Thus 0.3 g of the quaternized beads was boiled in 20 ml of 20% KOH solution for 2 h. The mixture was filtered and washed with 30 ml distilled water. The filtrate and washing were combined and neutralized with 3 M HNO₃. The solution was transferred in a 100 ml volumetric flask. The analysis of the iodide was performed iodometrically¹⁸. The iodide content of the product indicates quantitative quaternization. The product contains an iodide ion per nitrogen centre approximately.

Sorption and desorption experiment :

Sorption experiments were carried out by batch method. To determine the amount of chromate adsorbed, 0.2 g quaternized product (QP4VP) was taken into a 100 ml beaker with 25 ml chromate solution. The pH (1–8), time (15–60 min), temperature (5–55 °C) and agitation speed (90–100 rpm) of the reaction medium was maintained as per standard method¹⁶. For the study of sorption kinetics, 1 ml sample solution was withdrawn each time from the reaction mixture by a syringe at a gap of fixed interval and estimated chromate spectrometrically¹⁶ using UV-VIS-NIR spectrometer (Shimadzu UV-PC). The amount of Cr^{VI} adsorbed was calculated using the relationship¹⁷ :

$$q_t = (W_i - W_f)/m \quad (1)$$

The parameter q_t is the Cr^{VI} adsorbed per unit mass of the QP4VP (q_t is popularly known as sorption capacity, expressed in mg g⁻¹). The parameters W_i and W_f are the initial and residual amount of Cr^{VI} (mg) respectively and m represents mass of the sorbent.

For desorption study, 0.2 g QP4VP was taken in a 100 ml beaker with 25 ml of Cr^{VI} solution (96.47 ppm)

and kept for 1 h at room temperature. The absorbed Cr^{VI} was then subjected to various stripping agents to desorb chromate.

All the experiments were conducted thrice under the same conditions and the relative error was less than 5% and the reproducibility of the results was greater than 95%. The results were reported as mean values.

Characterization of solid phase :

The characterization of solid phase (QP4VP) was performed both in presence and absence of Cr^{VI}. The chromate sorption was determined with Cr^{VI} solution (96.47 ppm) at pH 5.6 with an agitation time 60 min. After this period, the solid phase was dried and analyzed by FTIR, TGA, DTA and SEM. The FTIR spectrum was recorded using KBr pellets by Shimadzu-8400S spectrometer. TGA and DTA were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer TGA/DTA (STA-6000) thermal analyzer in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. SEM of the solid phase was conducted using JEOL SEM 6360 apparatus.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of quaternized polymer :

The quaternized poly(4-vinyl pyridine) was synthesized using 2% cross-linked poly(4-vinyl pyridine), iodoethane and green solvent (water) with the help of ultrasound. The size, surface area and anion exchange capacity of the quaternized product was found to be 0.25–0.50 mm, 9.2 m² g⁻¹, 4.5 meq g⁻¹ respectively. These parameters are much improved than commercially available widely used anion exchanger Amberlite-400 and comparable to that of ReillexTM HPQ¹². The scanning electron micrograph (Fig. 1) showed the bead shape and gel morphological structures of the prepared polymer.

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrograph of the quaternized polymer, QP4VP.

FTIR analysis :

Fig. 2 shows the FTIR spectra of P4VP (A), QP4VP (B) and QP4VP loaded with Cr^{VI} (C) at pH 5.6. The comparison of the spectra of P4VP and QP4VP revealed that a new peak at 1640 cm⁻¹ is appeared in B and the characteristic band at 1600 cm⁻¹ is disappeared from A.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of P4VP (A), QP4VP (B) and QP4VP loaded with Cr^{VI} (C).

The peaks at 1600 and 1640 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to tertiary^{3,13} and quaternary ammonium^{3,13} groups respectively. Thus, the complete shifting of peak from 1600 to 1640 cm⁻¹, may be treated as quantitative quaternization of P4VP. Fig. 2C shows characteristic signal of Cr–O bond¹⁵ of both CrO₄²⁻ and Cr₂O₇²⁻ at 875 cm⁻¹. The result confirms the retention of Cr^{VI} by QP4VP. On the basis of FTIR study a model of interaction between QP4VP and Cr^{VI} has been proposed (Fig. 3)³.

Fig. 3. Model proposed for interaction between QP4VP and Cr^{VI} at different pH.

Fig. 4. TGA of P4VP (A), QP4VP (B) and Cr^{VI} loaded QP4VP (C).

TGA analysis :

Fig. 4 shows the thermal degradation profile of P4VP (A), QP4VP (B) and Cr^{VI} loaded QP4VP (C). The profile reveals that quaternized products (B and C) are less stable than starting material (A) as the decomposition starts around 400 and 500 °C for the former and later case respectively. Besides, it can be observed that P4VP and QP4VP have a total mass loss of 100%, but the Cr^{VI} loaded species shows mass loss of approximately 90%. The remaining 10% mass corresponds to the presence of Cr^{VI} oxides without decomposition. As can be seen, there is, in all cases, a slight weight loss around 100 °C, which can be attributed to the evaporation of water molecules. Moreover, the derivatives of P4VP contain some of residual quaternizing agent ethyl iodide whose boiling point is 70 °C. The loss of residual quaternizing agent is reflected from the degradation pattern between 200–300 °C. In addition, the degradation mechanism of QP4VP is bimodal as compared to that of P4VP which is unimodal.

Effect of sorbate dose on sorption :

Effect of chromium ions (sorbate) present initially in the aqueous solution was studied in order to assess the concentration range of chromium which can be treated by the present material. The extent of sorption (q_t) increased with the increase of sorbate dose (5–1000 mg L⁻¹) reaching a plateau at about 1000 mg L⁻¹, which

corresponds to 100% use of the ion exchange capacity. The maximum sorption capacity was found to be 120 mg g⁻¹, which may be treated as better results compared to the poly(4-vinyl pyridine) quaternized with 2-chloroacetamide¹⁴ (95 mg g⁻¹), benzyl chloride¹⁷ (70 mg g⁻¹), 2-chloroacetone¹⁷ (75 mg g⁻¹), and commercially available anion exchange, Amberlite-400¹² (108 mg g⁻¹) and ReillexTM HPQ¹² (112 mg g⁻¹).

Effect of pH on sorption :

Sorption of chromium was studied at various pH values to determine the optimum pH range for its removal and the results are presented in Fig. 5. The pH was adjusted with the additions of diluted sodium acetate and acetic acid. The sorption of Cr^{VI} is fruitful at pH values between 3.0 and 8.0. It is noteworthy to mention here that most of the anion exchange resin functions well between 3.0 and 5.0 (acidic medium) and deactivates in the basic medium. The favorable wide pH range (both acidic and basic) may be explained from the model (Fig. 3). At very low pH (< 3), the Cr^{VI} remains mainly as non-ionic form (H₂CrO₄), which accounts for its low sorption. At pH > 8, the hydroxyl ion competes with chromate ion resulting low chromium sorption. The rest of the experiment was done at pH 5.6, because pH of effluent of many chrome industry lies in the same order.

The pH dependent sorption mainly takes place through

Fig. 5. Variation of sorption capacity with pH. [Sorbent dose = 8 g/L, sorbate dose = 47.16 ppm, Temperature = 30 °C].

ion exchange process [eq. (2)]. It was supported by the fact that the addition of halide desorbs the chromate ion. Potassium iodide acts as very good stripping agent for the present system.

Effect of sorbent dose :

To evaluate the efficiency of quaternized polymer (sorbent) on the removal of Cr^{VI}, sorption experiments were conducted with different doses of the sorbent in the range 5–15 g L⁻¹. It was observed that the sorption level increases with increasing the resin amount but the sorption capacity (the amount absorbed per unit mass) decreases. It is readily understood that the number of available sorption site increases by increasing the resin amount and it, therefore results in the increase of removal efficiency. In the present study, all the experiments were done at 8 g L⁻¹ of sorbent to minimize the analytical errors.

Sorption kinetics :

It is a well-established fact that the sorption of ions from aqueous solutions is reversible and follows reversible first order kinetic when a single species is considered on a heterogeneous surface¹⁶. The progress of the sorption process was monitored at different time intervals.

The Cr^{VI} sorption with respect to time was smooth and continuous leading to saturation after an hour showing monolayer coverage of metal ions on the surface of the resin.

Effect of the SO₄²⁻ and Cl⁻ as competitive ions :

Since sulfate and chloride are the predominant anionic species in cooling tower blow-down, the resin must have high sorption selectivity for Cr^{VI} over these competing anions. To measure the selectivity, equilibrium chromate sorption was measured in the presence of 200-fold molar excess of SO₄²⁻ and 400-fold molar excess of Cl⁻ at different levels of pH of the aqueous medium. The selectivity (S) defined¹² as : S = (Cr^{VI} sorption in presence of SO₄²⁻/Cl⁻)/(Cr^{VI} sorption in absence of SO₄²⁻/Cl⁻).

The selectivity value was found to be greater than 0.5 over the pH range 3 to 8, which suggested the preference of chromate over both sulfate and chloride. It is well-known that the selectivity order for the common anions of the commercially available styrene anion exchanger is : SO₄²⁻ > I⁻ > CrO₄²⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. In our case, the synthesized resin showed a reversal selectivity namely CrO₄²⁻ > SO₄²⁻ > Cl⁻.

It is reported¹² that at high concentration of bisulfate (pK₂ = 2.1) and chloride, HCrO₄⁻ may form mononuclear complexes [(eqs. (3) and (4)] at acidic medium.

Mononuclear Cr^{VI} complexes (CrSO₄²⁻ and CrO₃Cl⁻) are likely to be present in the exchanger phase at fairly high HSO₄⁻ and Cl⁻ level at the acidic medium. Thus the synthesized polymer had little preference below pH 3. Strong competition for exchange sites by SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻ and OH⁻ at alkaline pH where the aforesaid mononuclear complex might not form and was possibly responsible for the sharp fall in Cr^{VI} sorption at pH > 8.

Sorption isotherms :

The effect of temperature on the sorption has been studied by performing sorption experiments in the temperature range of 5–55 °C. The result suggests that the

equilibrium reaches rapidly with the increasing temperature. For the equilibrium sorption isotherm study in a two-component system consisting of sorbent and solution, a plot of the solute concentration in the solid phase, Q (mg g^{-1}) as a function of the solute concentration in the solution, C_e (mg L^{-1}) at equilibrium was drawn. In a solid liquid system, the sorption resulted in the removal of solute from the solution onto solid surface until the remaining solute in the solution is in dynamic equilibrium with solute on the solid phase.

The Langmuir equation⁷ was basically derived for the sorption of gases on the solid surface. Nevertheless, it has been extended to include the sorption of solute at solid-liquid interface^{15,17}. The Langmuir isotherm is valid for monolayer sorption onto the surface containing a finite number of identical sites and the standard mathematical representation is :

$$C_e/q_e = 1/(Q_m \times b) + C_e/Q_m \quad (5)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration of chromium in the solution (mg L^{-1}); q_e , the amount of the retained chromium (mg g^{-1}); Q_m is the maximum sorption capacity (mg g^{-1}) and b is the Langmuir constant related to the affinity of binding sites. The essential feature of Langmuir sorption can be expressed by means of R_L , a dimensionless constant referred to as a separation factor or equilibrium parameter for the prediction if the sorption system is favorable or not. R_L can be calculated using the equation :

$$R_L = 1/(1 + b \cdot C_0) \quad (6)$$

C_0 is the initial concentration of the chromate solution (mg L^{-1}).

The Freundlich isotherm model⁷ assumes that the sorption of metal ions occurs on a heterogeneous sorbent surface. Freundlich equation is expressed as :

$$\log(Q/m) = \log K_F + (1/n) \log C_e \quad (7)$$

Q is the amount of retained chromium (mg g^{-1}); m is the amount of the resin (g L^{-1}); C_e is the concentration at equilibrium (mg L^{-1}); K_F and n are Freundlich constants.

The Langmuir and Freundlich sorption parameters were determined by plotting the experimental data based on eqs. (5) and (7) respectively. The parameters were determined and their corresponding correlation coefficient (R^2) were listed in Table 1. The parameters clearly suggests for favourable sorption of chromate ions. The R_L values obtained in the present case are less than 1 and very close to 0 and therefore, they also indicate a favourable sorption.

Desorption study :

QP4VP (0.2 g) was taken in a 100 ml beaker with 25 ml of Cr^{VI} solution (96.47 ppm) at pH 5.6 and kept for 1 h at room temperature. The absorbed Cr^{VI} was then subjected to various stripping agents such as Na_2CO_3 , NaOH , NaCl and KI to desorb chromate. KI ($> 1 M$) was found to be the most fruitful stripping agents. It desorbed to the extent of 88.88%. Other agents gave fairly lesser extent of desorption.

Conclusion :

Quaternization of poly(4-vinyl pyridine) with iodoethane has been achieved in aqueous medium sonochemically. The novelty of the quaternization method is quantitative as well as green. The synthesized resin may be used to remove and recover Cr^{VI} from the aqueous solution through batch method within the pH range 3–8 at ambient temperature. Competitive ions like SO_4^{2-} and Cl^- do not hamper the Cr^{VI} sorption up to pH 8. The sorption and desorption of Cr^{VI} mainly take place through ion exchange process. Sorption takes place very quickly. Isothermal sorption experimental data obey both Langmuir and Freundlich model. Potassium iodide behaves as a fruitful stripping agent.

Table 1. Values of Langmuir and Freundlich constants for the sorption of Cr^{VI}

T (K)	Langmuir constants				Freundlich constants		
	R_L	Q_m	b	R^2	n	K_F	R^2
278	5.031×10^{-3}	12.74	2.06	0.6234	0.30	10.51	0.9834
303	2.04×10^{-3}	8.39	5.09	0.9866	0.25	9.41	0.9878
328	1.34×10^{-3}	7.41	7.71	0.9916	0.456	10.47	0.9982

Sorbent dose = 8 g/L, sorbate dose = 47.16 ppm, Temperature = 5–55 °C, pH = 4.01.

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